

ANCIENT PHILOSOPHY – THE SOURCE OF INDIVIDUAL RATIONALISM

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the study of the philosophical views of the philosopher-writer L.N.Tolstoy concerning the problems of individualism and the origins of their occurrence in the cultural space of peoples. The evolution of Tolstoy's philosophical observations and conclusions allows us to interpret the concept of "individualism" and its connection with the subsequent degradation of personality. In the context of this article, we give examples of the manifestation of an individualistic worldview at an early stage of the development of human civilization and its influence on the worldview of mankind to the present day on the example of literary motifs.

Keywords: national peculiarities, ancient literature, problems of the historical development of mankind, individualism, rationalism, collectivism, irrationality, conciliarity.

Introduction

Ancient religions, religions of the East and Christianity of Western Europe of the Middle Ages interpreted and directed public consciousness in different ways to understand the place of man in society. The author opposes an individual or mass (conciliar) perception of the world around us, which has a different interpretation at the religious level, which in the 19th century will receive a philosophical form from European and Russian thinkers.

The philosophical teachings of antiquity had a great influence on the formation of Western individualism, where issues of freedom, equality and certain values are realized exclusively through the prism of an individual worldview. This has led to a great civilizational leap, when a person creates a state, a socio-economic formation, engages in science and secularizes culture. However, later the process, becoming irreversible, leads society to the absolutization of the role of the individual, this becomes an end in itself. Faith, ethics, morality and man are subordinated to this superreality. Thus, individualism is degenerating, and society is losing its vitality.

The purpose of the study

The purpose of the research is to consider issues related to the emergence of the concept of "individualism", its manifestation in the works of ancient philosophers and its embodiment in the epic novel by L.N. Tolstoy "War and Peace".

Materials and methods of research

The material for the study is literary articles about the work of L.N.Tolstoy, studies of the novel "War and Peace" - the views of Russian cultural philosophy on the manifestation of individualism in society, which, in the interpretation of L.N.Tolstoy, leads to an egoistic perception of reality and subsequent degradation of personality. The study used methods of comparative research, literary analysis and a method of quantitative processing of the data obtained.

Results and discussion

So, ancient individualism and the "I-concept" created by it, which will be discussed, were considered by some Greek philosophers as one of the fundamental elements of ancient civilization.

One of these forms of worldview is moral relativism. At its origins are the Greek philosophers Heraclitus, Democritus, Empedocles and others. Relativism assumes that absolute "good" and "evil" do not exist, mandatory moral norms are denied, and the principle of "everything is allowed" becomes dominant.

Plato in the dialogue "Kratilus" gives the following definition: "(Protagoras said) that the measure of all things is man—and therefore, what things seem to me, they will be for me, and what they are for you, they will be for you." Therefore, the criterion and source of truth is a person, an individual in itself.

The philosopher Protagoras suggested that a person has freedom of choice, that is, the right to call this or that phenomenon the truth. This is reserved for the individual. (In the novel "War and Peace", this thesis is developed by Tolstoy on the example of Elena Kuragina, namely her transition from Orthodoxy to Catholicism, betrayal of her husband and an affair with Dolokhov).

Ancient individualism manifested itself in all spheres of social, political and cultural life of slave-owning states. In literature, the "I-concept" is especially evident in the legends and myths of Ancient Greece. The Olympian gods, demigods, the greatest heroes of the Iliad and the Odyssey, their deeds and exploits are described exclusively from the point of view of individual heroic actions.

In Homer's Iliad there is no pathos of collectivism, but there is the heroism of individual heroes: Achilles and Hector, Ajax, Odysseus.

In The Odyssey, the entire plot is based on one character, after whom the entire heroic epic is named. The author does not describe in detail the satellites of the Odyssey, and many of them remain nameless, included in the storyline of one hero.

So, ancient individualism has left its mark on the self-awareness and worldview of entire societies and peoples. Did there exist in ancient times a form of social perception other than individualism? This form was "collectivism".

For a detailed consideration of the "we-concept", it should be noted that collectivism does not fully reflect the full philosophical understanding of this concept, but is one of the forms of its manifestation.

The ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle argued that "man is by nature a political being" and is not self-sufficient by nature. Only the state can be self-sufficient, and a person outside the state is an animal or a deity.

Aristotle is a figure in philosophy in which Hellenic collectivism transforms into ideas of individualism. Although he claims that "man is a social being to a greater extent than bees and all kinds of herd animals," he nevertheless believes that "people care most about what belongs to them personally." (In the novel "War and Peace" this thesis is clearly reflected in the image of Napoleon, who noticed: "Public opinion always has the last word," but at the same time, "people are better governed by their vices than their virtues.")

During the period of late Roman history, which was marked by the spread of Christianity in Europe, there was a development of collectivism based on some provisions of the Bible. The reflection of the "I-concept" and "we-concept" in European culture manifested itself precisely

in the context of early Christianity in a slave-owning society, when the concepts of "Christian community" and "labor collective" sometimes had the same meaning. The Book of Acts of the Apostles says: "All the believers were together, and they had everything in common."

Eastern philosophy and cultural studies in relation to the "I-concept" and "We-concept" gives a slightly different interpretation. Of course, one of the world's religions, Islam, plays an important role in shaping the "Eastern" worldview. Islam is a monotheistic religion based on the Holy Book of the Koran, and the prophet Muhammad S.A.V. is recognized as the last prophet sent by God to people. Islam recognizes all prophets, both Jewish and Christian (Abraham - Ibrohim, David - Dovut, Moses - Musa, Jesus - Esau). Islam also recognizes the sacred books of both religions. However, the attitude towards life among Muslims is radically different. It should be noted that the principle of collectivism is very strongly developed in Muslim society. Since the 7th century AD, the Muslim Ummah or "Jamaat" has emerged, uniting all people who profess Islam. There are Jewish and Christian Ummahs, which, according to Muslims, unite people who "obey their prophet."

A devout Muslim lives trying to maintain balance in everything, not trying to dominate any aspect of his life. The real and the ideal, the material and the spiritual, the mundane and the afterlife, divine revelation and human reason, collectivism and idealism – in all this, a Muslim must observe the principle of balance and the same approach. In Islam, this principle sounds like "al-wasitaya", which is discussed in detail in the work of the Uzbek scholar-theologian Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf "Wasitaya – a way of life".

In Europe, the Medieval period was marked by an important event that occurred due to political, geographical, national and religious reasons. We are talking about the division of a Single Church into three separate denominations, independent of each other.

The Catholic Church, Orthodoxy and, later, Protestantism, based on the same doctrine, radically diverged ideologically, which also influenced the cultural life of that time.

Conclusion

Catholicism, as the dominant religion of most of Europe, introduced into the cultural life of European peoples those ideas of individualism that were transferred to the Middle Ages from antiquity. It is enough to recall one of the early medieval epics, The Song of Roland, where, thanks to the heroism of one knight, one of the memorable pages of Frankish history is glorified. The "I-concept" will manifest itself in other genres of medieval literature. The Scandinavian sagas "The Elder Edda", "The Saga of Magnus the Good", "The Sagas of Kings" have one common theme - stories about God or the feat of a great hero.

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